

Title:

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A MACHINE LEARNING BASED
ASA-SCORE TO IDENTIFY CANDIDATES FOR COMPREHENSIVE
PREOPERATIVE SCREENING AND RISK STRATIFICATION (Galda-score)

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Short title: Galda-score: a machine learning based preoperative risk model

Summary

Background: The American Society of Anesthesiologists Physical Status (ASA-PS) classification system, assesses pre-anesthesia medical comorbidities to guide resource allocation and anticipate perioperative risks. To improve its precision and reliability, the integration of machine learning (ML) techniques allows for the development of a model that can suggest ASA-PS scores. This study aims to use machine learning (ML) to develop a scoring system (Galda-score) that enhances the accuracy of the ASA-PS. In doing so, it provides clinicians with data-driven support, improving decision-making and optimizing the utilization of healthcare resources.

Methods: This retrospective cohort study, conducted from 2019 to 2022 across five Basque Country hospitals, analyzed anonymized data from surgical patients. Data on demographics and comorbidities (ICD-10 codes), were collected and processed. A predictive model for preoperative status was developed and validated using XGBoost, with the data divided into 80% training and 20% testing subsets to avoid information leakage

The model's performance was assessed through sensitivity, specificity, and ROC curve analysis. External validation was carried out with a 2022 cohort, ensuring robustness across different datasets. Model development utilized Python and SAS, with R software for final calibration.

Results: In this study, 24,959 patients were analyzed in the development set, and 75,773 in the external validation set. Our Galda-score was compared with the

ASA-PS. Key predictors of ASA status, including age, arrhythmia, hypertension, and obesity, were identified by the XGBoost model. The model's predictive performance and calibration were assessed, demonstrating excellent sensitivity and specificity across various risk groups, with the negative predictive value ranging from 0.77 to 0.93.

Conclusions: This retrospective cohort study used Machine Learning to develop the Galda-Score, which correlates well with ASA-PS predictions. It demonstrated improvements in preoperative risk assessments using demographic and comorbidity data. Validation confirmed its reliability compared to traditional assessments, highlighting its potential as a supplementary preoperative tool.

Introduction

The American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) Physical Status (PS) Classification System is a widely used tool for assessing and communicating a patient's pre-anesthesia medical co-morbidities. Originally developed in 1941 (Mayhew et al., 2019; Saklad, 1941; Sweitzer, 2017), the ASA-PS system assigns scores ranging from 1 (indicating a healthy patient) to 6 (representing a brain-dead organ donor). Its primary purpose is to aid physician anesthesiologists and healthcare providers in evaluating surgical patients, with the aim of predicting perioperative risks and optimizing resource allocation.

However, the application of the ASA-PS score has evolved over time, and it is now employed not only as a tool for assessing a patient's health status but also as a predictor of various surgical outcomes, including operating times, hospital length of stay, postoperative infection rates, necessity of blood transfusion, and overall morbidity and mortality rates (Akhtar et al., 2020; Bjorgul et al., 2010; Carey et al., 2006; Dalton et al., 2011; Dripps et al., 1961; Hightower et al., 2010; Lee et al., 1999; Magi, 1997; Prause et al., 1997; Ridgeway et al., 2005; Tang et al., 2001). This shift in usage has raised concerns about variability in its assignment among physician anesthesiologists, leading to inconsistencies in patient risk stratification. (De Cassai et al., 2019; Haynes & Lawler, 1995; Knuf et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021; Sankar et al., 2014). In this context, inaccuracies in ASA-PS classification can result in either excessive or insufficient preoperative testing, potentially leading to delays in surgery or even cancellations on the day of the procedure (Wongtangman et al., 2023).

Machine Learning has been applied to predict various medical outcomes, including intraoperative hypotension, which is linked to postoperative complications and an eightfold increase in mortality. However, there are gaps between these predictive tools and their clinical use by anesthesiologists (Dong et al., 2024).

Algorithms in artificial intelligence are designed to identify patterns in complex datasets, such as clinical patient data (Gálvez et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2018). This approach aims to enhance the ASA PS scoring system by integrating Machine Learning (ML) techniques to enhance and streamline the ASA PS score calculation process. Leveraging ML in the collection of clinical data can allow an objective and uniform determination of ASA PS scores by discerning among several patient characteristics. Moreover, this analysis can unveil the correlations between co-morbidities and the corresponding ASA PS scores, potentially leading to the establishment of a standardized approach for assigning ASA PS scores (Lee et al., 1999). This advancement, not only seeks to improve the precision of ASA-PS categorization, but also has the potential to enhance patient outcomes through the prediction of 30-day mortality, the risk of admission to the intensive care unit (ICU), and the likelihood of unfavorable discharge to nursing homes. In the era of precision medicine, the development and validation of these predictive models offer the potential to optimize patient care during the perioperative period (ChatGPT, n.d.).

The objective of this article is not to establish a new ASA-PS score but rather to use Machine Learning (ML) techniques to formulate a predictive score similar to the approach taken in Ferrari's study within the pediatric population (Ferrari et al., 2023).

Methods

1. Study design

The Basque Country Ethics committee (PI2023/029) approved the data collection protocol and waiver of informed consent forms. The study was carried out in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations.

This is a retrospective cohort study recruiting surgical patients at five public hospitals locations in the Basque Country between 2019 and 2022. We used anonymized patient level data from patients in the waiting list to be intervened. Participating hospitals serve a population of approximately 1.2 million and provide tertiary referral services to the surrounding region.

All patients who operated at participant centers except for obstetrics patients and cardiac surgery were included.

Data was internally stored and managed by the Osakidetza-Basque Public Health System. After anonymization and removal of protected health information, the data were released in a text-delimited format for research purposes. Patient-level data were collected for the initial analyses of the study.

2. Data preparation:

Demographic data, including variables such as age and sex, along with information on addictions, comorbidities, and baseline medical treatments at the time of surgery, were collected. Comorbidities were assessed based on International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision codes that were active on the patient's Electronic Health Records. We categorized them according to whether the date of diagnosis was in the previous year or earlier. Baseline treatments were assessed based on the Anatomical,

Therapeutic and Chemical/Defined Daily Dose (ATC/DDD) index in the EHR, and we categorized them into treatments prescribed in the last 6 months, between > 6 and 12 months earlier and between > 12 months and 5 years earlier (older treatments being excluded). Patients were considered to have no comorbidities or treatments if none were documented in the EHR.

Initially, factors such as tobacco and alcohol use, and hyperfeeding were considered but were ultimately excluded from the analysis. Additionally, we proposed the inclusion of analytical data and routine treatments in the model to enhance its predictive capacity. However, subsequent implementation showed that these did not improve the model, leading to its exclusion.

The outcome measure was anesthesiologist's ASA PS (A-ASA) scale recorded at Electronic Health Record. We constructed a model using classical modeling techniques combined with the GALDA-SCORE Machine Learning techniques named (The acronym originates from the University Hospital of Galdakao, where it was developed. It reflects the institution's contribution to the research and serves as a reference to the hospital's name.)

2.1 Datasets

1. Development and internal validation dataset. For model development, the observations in which the A-ASA PS was not collected, the one in which the ASA indicator was V and obstetric patients were excluded; the total number of interventions was divided into two sets: training (80% between January 2019 and December 2021) and test (20% between January 2019 and December 2021). Any patients appearing in the test data set were removed from the training data set to avoid cross set duplication. The A-ASA PS assigned by the anesthesiologist clinician on the

day of surgery was used as the gold standard. Only patients with complete data records were included in the analysis.

An exploratory analysis of the data was performed, statistical and visualization techniques were used to evaluate the structure and distribution of the data, data set quality and determine initial patterns that may predict the relationship between the selected variables considered and the A-ASA PS. After the initial data evaluation, algorithmic techniques were identified, as well as the methodology and test indicators. A selection of relevant data subsets was made from the available data catalog to cover all the identified cases. A selection of relevant variables was made, preprocessing techniques were applied, and data sets were constructed for training and validation of the models.

Due to the large class imbalance in the data set, the classes considered were balanced. Thus, the number of elements in the majority sample (low-risk patients) was reduced. This balancing was applied by taking 25% more ASA I/II samples from those available for ASA III/IV (high-risk patients). On these already balanced samples, the training and test partitioning were applied.

2. *Validation dataset.* Furthermore, a retrospective validation set of patients, independent from the original datasets, referred to as the validation dataset, was composed of other patients whose surgeries were between January 2022 and December 2022. This cohort was recruited from different hospitals participating in the study, Galdakao-Usansolo University Hospital (GUH), Urduliz Hospital (UH), Basurto University Hospital (BUH), Donostia University Hospital (DUH) and Araba University Hospital (AUH). This retrospective cohort, once the ASA-PS prediction

model had been developed and tested, was used for external validation and it was pre-processed using the same protocol used in the development dataset.

3. Model input variables

We trained the model to predict the A-ASA-PS (I-IV) as a categorical outcome.

The model was created using a set of variables from the following categories: patients' demographic data and International Classification of Diseases (ICD)-based co-morbidities. Categorical variables were split into binary input features, resulting in a total of thirty one input features for model training.

4. Development and validation of the predictive model

After evaluating the best available algorithmic alternatives through normalization, parameter calibration, training and evaluation, several ML models were implemented and validated, and the best model was selected in terms of predictive capacity. The Machine Learning method finally chosen to predict the categorical outcome (ASA-PS class I to IV) from the thirty one input data was XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) Bentéjac, C., Csörgo, A., & Martínez-Muñoz, G. (2019). A comparative analysis of gradient boosting algorithms. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 54, 1937 - 1967, based on triage decision process. Machine Learning boosting is a method that creates an ensemble set. An ensemble is a combination of simple individual models that together create a more powerful one. It begins by fitting an initial model (a regression or classification tree) to the data. Then, a second model is built that focuses on accurately predicting the observations that the first model mispredicted. The

combination of these two models is expected to be better than each individual one. This enhancing process is repeated several times, with each successive model, attempting to correct the deficiencies of the combined boosting set containing all the previous models. The statistical explanation is that the different weak predictors can learn different ways of classifying a piece of data and their consensus reduces the risk of making a bad choice.

Binary classification models were generated for different phases of the estimation. First, a model was generated to determine the probability of being a high-risk patient (ASA PS III/IV) versus being a low-risk patient (ASA PS I/II). In order to refine the estimate produced, binary classification models were trained for the separation between ASA I, II, III and IV.

In our development set, the classes considered were balanced. Then, the total number of interventions was divided into the two sets of training and test. Once these subsets have been generated, the model was trained and internally validated. Subsequently, the most influential variables in the estimation were obtained. Finally, the training and validation error tables, as well as the area under the ROC curve (AUC) and other graphs for the analysis of the estimates were calculated.

First, the performance of the binary classification models were analyzed, both for the separation between ASA I/II and III/IV and for the subsequent refinement between I and II or III and IV. Next, individuals detected as highly discordant by healthcare personnel were analyzed. Finally, those patients with more than two classes of difference detected were automatically analyzed individually. These analyses of individuals make it possible to answer the reasons for the difference between the models' and the health personnel's estimates.

The Galda-score indicator was estimated for all patients available on the information extracted. Whenever the ASA probability was III/IV and greater than 0.5, it was also estimated whether the indicator was III or IV. Otherwise, the same was done by determining whether the indicator was I or II.

A descriptive analysis of the entire sample and univariate analysis between original ASA I/II and ASA III/IV was performed by frequencies and percentages for categorical data, while means and standard deviations were used for continuous variables. Differences according to ASA level was performed using Chi-square test for categorical variables and Wilcoxon test for continuous variables. We considered a difference of >2% between cohorts to be clinically significant. While statistical significance was assessed using standard methods, we recognized that small statistically significant differences may not always translate to meaningful clinical impacts. Therefore, we established this 2% threshold as a benchmark for clinical relevance when comparing groups.

In order to determine the overall quality of the model, the confusion matrix of the joint system is shown. Taking into account the distribution of the predictive probability of the outcome, four groups of risk were created. The optimal thresholds of the predictive probability were determined with the CatPedri function of the R package CatPedri (I et al., s. f.)

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The performance of the risk classification was analyzed by comparing ASA III/IV rate between categories, and calculating AUC. Finally, sensitivity, specificity, predictive positive value (PPV) and predictive negative value (NPV) were calculated

of each cut-off point. E.W. Steyerberg, Validation of prediction models, in: Clinical Prediction Models, Springer, New York, 2009, pp. 299–310. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-77244-8_17

The contribution of each characteristic was assessed using the SHapley additional explanations method (SHAP). SHAP values assess the significance of the result of including a feature for all feature combinations except that feature. Features shown in blue indicate that their values are less likely to predict the outcome, while values in red are more likely to predict the outcome⁴.

External validation

The analysis of the results obtained by the preoperative risk estimation models on the external population and independently of the data considered for the generation of these models are shown. For these analysis the available comorbidity data are considered, as well as the age and sex of the different patients.

The model was externally validated by comparing the ability of the models to handle such information.

First, the performance of the binary classification models was analyzed, both for the separation between ASA I/II and III/IV and for the subsequent refinement between I and II or III and IV. Next, individuals detected as highly discordant by healthcare personnel were analyzed.

Estimation of the ASA indicator was performed for all patients available on the information extracted. Whenever the probability that the ASA was III/IV was greater

than 0.5, it was also estimated whether the indicator is III or IV. Otherwise, the same was done by determining whether the indicator was I or II.

In order to determine the overall quality of the model, the joint confusion matrix, ROC curve, precision recall curve and calibration plot are shown.

SAS software was used for the univariate analysis, version 9.4 (SAS Institute, Carey, NC, USA) and Python 3.8 (Python Software Foundation, <http://www.python.org>) to pre-process data and develop the model with the XGBoost supervised machine learning method (<https://xgboost.ai/>). Finally, the model was calibrated using R software 4.1.2 (<http://www.r-project.org>)

Results

Data collection. For the analysis, 24959 were included in the data preprocessing set of development and internal validation dataset, while 75773 were included in the external validation set (Figure 1). There were statistically significant differences between percentages of patients with ASA III/IV in both datasets (44,5% vs 25.6%, $p = <.0001$)

Datasets. Table 1 shows the characteristics of datasets. Clinically significant differences were encountered in prevalence of COPD, diabetes without organ damage, hypercholesterolemia and malignant tumor between databases, being more frequent those comorbidities in external validation cohort. Table 1 also shows univariate analysis, we found, in all sociodemographic and comorbidities, statistically significant differences in outcome through databases.

Development and validation of the predictive model.

Figure 2 shows main variables in the XGBoost model. We used SHAP values to provide consistent and locally accurate attribution values for each feature within the prediction model. The strongest predictors of ASA were age, sex, arrhythmia, hipertension, dm without complications and obesity followed by combination of comorbidities, being COPD, cardiovascular diseases and malignancy among them. The predictive performance of the XGBoost model by ROC and precision-recall curves in the derivation and validation sets are shown in Figure 3 and calibration plots in Figure 4. The model has a predictive capacity (AUC) of 0.720 (0.711-0.724) in the derivation set and 0.793 (0.790-0.797) in validation.

We explored the distribution of the outcome across the predicted probability based on the scores from the XGBoost classifier. We considered three different cut-off points to classify patients as reaching or not reaching the endpoint based on predicted values of

probability. Table 2 shows the performance parameters for each cut-off point, the lowest group being the most sensitive and the highest group the most specific. The negative predictive value ranged between 0.77 and 0.93 across the risk groups in the derivation sample and 0.83-0.95 in the validation dataset. In addition, the variable representing patients risk stratification was defined considering the cut-off points mentioned above and creating complementary risk groups.

Discussion

This retrospective cohort study, conducted in public hospitals in the Basque Country, robustly applies Machine Learning techniques, specifically XGBoost, based on preoperative data from Electronic Health Records (EHR), to predict patient health status. This study introduces a new scoring system, the Galda-score, which correlates well with the American Society of Anesthesiologists Physical Status (ASA-PS) scale. By utilizing a comprehensive dataset that includes demographic data and comorbidities coded with ICD-10, this study demonstrates the feasibility of using such data to refine preoperative risk assessments for surgical patients. Additionally, we explore the emerging potential of Machine Learning models like the ML-PS model proposed by Wongtangman et al. (Wongtangman et al., 2023) and Zhang and Fabbri (Zhang et al., 2018), which offer a standardized, provider-independent approach to predicting ASA, thereby enhancing the accuracy and reliability of preoperative evaluations.

Similar to findings by Wongtangman, our study observes that anesthesia providers more often assign ASA-PS indicative of mild systemic disease (ASA II) or severe but non-life-threatening systemic disease (ASA III), rather than extreme conclusions (no disease or life-threatening disease). This central tendency bias—where evaluators

place most items in the middle of a scale—is notable. The ASA-PS descriptions are not based on objectively measurable parameters; for example, ASA-PS II is defined as "mild diseases without substantial functional limitations," yet there are no universally accepted criteria to define "substantial functional limitation."

We would say this validation process demonstrates that our Galda-score, derived from XGBoost, is at least as precise as the provider-derived ASA-PS score. However, it is challenging for anesthesiologists to pinpoint the true ASA-PS, as there is no definitive gold standard for chart review.

Our aim was to align closely with the ideas of ASA's inventor, Dr. Saklad, from his seminal 1941 paper in Anesthesiology. His goal was to create a tool to correlate the relationship between surgical outcomes, operative procedures, and patients' preoperative conditions. Thus, we believe it aligns with the principle of the scale to compare the two ASA-PS evaluation approaches with "outcomes". Future work will aim to compare the ASA-PS with our Galda-score against clinically significant external endpoints such as mortality, ICU admission, and adverse discharge disposition.

This research focuses on addressing a critical need in preoperative care by enhancing the precision of ASA-PS classifications, crucial for assessing surgical risk. The inclusion of a variety of input variables, refined through iterative consultations with hospital staff, highlights a thorough data preparation process aimed at optimizing the model's accuracy and relevance. The model's development and validation were rigorously conducted using a split-sample method to ensure that the training and test datasets were independent. This methodological rigor is essential to minimize information duplication across the two sets and to externally validate the model's

performance. The XGBoost algorithm, known for its effectiveness in handling complex datasets with unbalanced classifications, adeptly processed the binary and categorical distinctions within ASA-PS, thus providing a nuanced tool for clinical decision-making. Although this study has not identified new variables that determine patient complexity, and the mathematical analysis has dismissed the use of other variables such as treatment or analytical values due to their minimal contribution to the final model, it is of great significance that risk categorization can be performed automatically with the same rigor as that conducted by a clinician.

It is demonstrated, as in previous works, that providing objective, consistent ML predictions to anesthesiologists can reduce variation among providers. Employing such tools in a high-demand clinical environment, and an overloaded surgical workload, can be a first step toward a telematic preoperative management with an automated patient evaluation. This study emphasizes the value of applying ML methods to large patients data available to hospitals for assessing perioperative risk assessment.

Conclusions

The model's validation results, demonstrated through a quasi-experimental intervention study, confirmed its predictive capacity and reliability in comparison to traditional anesthesiologist assessments. This suggests that the model could potentially serve as a supplementary tool for preoperative assessment, helping to identify high-risk patients who may require more intensive care or specific interventions prior to undergoing surgery.

Notably, the study also highlighted challenges in distinguishing between closely ranked ASA classifications, particularly II and III as other similar works. This issue was reflected in the error rates and the occasional indecisiveness of the model around these classifications, where the ASA-PS probability was around 0.5. This uncertainty indicates a possible area for future improvement, potentially through the integration of additional variables or the refinement of the model's architecture to better delineate between these classes.

The study not only enhances our understanding of how Machine Learning can be applied in clinical settings to improve patient outcomes but also sets a precedent for future research in this area. The successful external validation across different hospital settings suggests that this model has a broad applicability and could be adopted more widely to improve the accuracy and efficiency of preoperative risk assessments. Once a robust correlation has been established between our Galda-score and the scales commonly used in clinical practice, our subsequent objective will be to demonstrate the enhanced predictive capability of our model in relation to key surgical outcomes, including mortality, hospital readmissions, and admissions to intensive care units. We anticipate detailing these findings in forthcoming publications. This advancement opens up extensive avenues for future exploration, enabling further refinement of the algorithm to account not only for patient-specific factors but also for the type of surgical procedure to be performed, which we plan to explore in subsequent studies.

This could ultimately lead to better patient stratification and tailored surgical interventions, thereby improving clinical outcomes in diverse healthcare settings.

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No competing interests declared

Authors must include data and statistical code accessibility statement, including a link to the repository they have used??

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